

A Review: Uses of Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Technique for Analysis of Bioactive Natural Compounds of Some Plants

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ABSTRACT

Chromatography is the term used to describe a separation technique in which a mobile phase carrying a mixture is caused to move in contact with a selectively absorbent stationary phase. It also plays a fundamental role as an analytical technique for quality control and standardization of phyto therapeutics. Gas Chromatography is used in the separation and analysis of multi component mixtures such as essential oils, hydrocarbons and solvents. Various temperature programs can be used to make the readings more meaningful; for example to differentiate between substances that behave similarly during the GC process. Intrinsically, with the use of the flame ionization detector and the electron capture detector (which have very high sensitivities) gas chromatography can quantitatively determine materials present at very low concentrations. Plants are a rich source of secondary metabolites with interesting biological activities. In general, these secondary metabolites are an important source with a variety of structural arrangements and properties. Gas chromatography - specifically gas-liquid chromatography - involves a sample being vapourised and injected onto the head of the chromatographic column. The sample is transported through the column by the flow of inert, gaseous mobile phase. The column itself contains a liquid stationary phase which is adsorbed onto the surface of an inert solid. The principle of gas chromatography is adsorption and partition. Within the family of chromatography- based methods gas chromatography (GC) is one of the most widely used techniques. GC-MS has become a highly recommended tool for monitoring and tracking organic pollutants in the environment. GC-MS is exclusively used for the analysis of esters, fatty acids, alcohols, aldehydes, terpenes etc. It is the key tool used in sports anti-doping laboratories to test athlete's urine samples for prohibited performanceenhancing drugs like anabolic steroids. Several GC-MS have left earth for the astro chemistry studies. As a unique and powerful technology the GC-MS provides a rare opportunity to perform the analysis of new compounds for characterization and identification of synthesized or derivatized compound.

Keyword: Chromatography, GC-MS, Bioactive compounds, Advantages, Applications.

INTRODUCTION

Gas chromatography has a very wide field of applications. But, its first and main area of use is in the separation and analysis of multi component mixtures such as essential oils, hydrocarbons and solvents¹⁻³. Intrinsically, with the use of the flame ionization detector and the electron capture detector (which have very high sensitivities) gas chromatography can quantitatively determine materials present at very low concentrations. It follows, that the second most important application area is in pollution studies, forensic work and general trace analysis. Because of its simplicity, sensitivity, and effectiveness in separating components of mixtures, gas chromatography is one of the most important tools in chemistry. It is widely used for quantitative and qualitative analysis of mixtures, for the purification of compounds, and for the determination of such thermo chemical constants as heats of solution and vaporization, vapor pressure, and activity coefficients⁴⁻⁹. A knowledge

of the chemical constituents of plants is desirable not only for the discovery of therapeutic agents, but also because such information may be of great value in disclosing new sources of economic phytochemicals for the synthesis of complex chemical substances and for discovering the actual significance of folkloric remedies. Higher plants as sources of bioactive compounds continue to play a dominant role in the maintenance of human health. Reports available on green plants represent a reservoir of effective chemotherapeutics, these are non-phytotoxic, more systemic and easily biodegradable¹¹⁻¹³. Hence a thorough validation of the herbal drugs has emerged as a new branch of science emphasizing and prioritizing the standardization of the natural drugs and products because several of the phytochemicals have complementary and overlapping mechanism of action. In recent years GC-MS studies have been increasingly applied for the analysis of medicinal plants as this technique has proved to be a valuable method for the analysis of non-polar

components and volatile essential oil, fatty acids, lipids and alkaloids¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

Advantages and Applications of GC-MS

Forensic and criminal cases

GC-MS can analyze the particles from suspect to correlate his involvement in case. The analysis of fire debris using GC-MS can be established by American Society for Testing Materials (ASTM) standard for fire debris analysis¹⁸⁻²⁹. It is also commonly used in forensic toxicology to find poisons, steroids in biological specimens of suspects, victims, or the deceased^{30,37}.

Environmental monitoring

The cost of GCMS equipment has decreased whereas the reliability has markedly increased. The determination of chloro-phenols in water and soil, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), unleaded gasoline, dioxins, dibenzofurans, organo-chlorine pesticides, herbicides, phenols, halogenated pesticides, sulphur in air is very convenient to be screened by this technique. It can be used to screen the degradation products of lignin in bio-mass research, pesticides in spinach³⁸⁻⁴⁷. Analysis of decacyclene, ovalene and even C60 degradation analysis of carbamazepine and its metabolites in treated sewage water and steroid can be done without derivatization^{48,49}.

Food, beverage, flavor and fragrance analysis

Foods and beverages have several aromatic compounds existing naturally in native state or formed while processing. GC-MS is also used to detect and measure contaminants, spoilage and adulteration of food, oil, butter, ghee that could be harmful and should to be controlled and checked as regulated by governmental agencies. It is used in the analysis of piperine⁵⁰, spearmint oil, lavender oil, essential oil, fragrance reference standards, perfumes, chiral compounds in essential oils, fragrances, menthol, allergens, olive oil, lemon oil, peppermint oil, yiang oil, straw berry syrup, butter triglycerides, residual pesticides in food and wine⁵¹.

Security and chemical warfare agent detection

Explosive detection systems have become a part of all United State airports, GC-MS. Is an essential part of chemical analysis unit. For enhancing capability in homeland security and public health preparedness, traditional GC-MS units with the transmission quadrupole mass spectrometers, as well as those with cylindrical ion trap (CIT-MS) and toroidal ion trap (T-ITMS) mass spectrometers have been modified for field portability and near real-time detection of chemical warfare agents (CWA) such as sarin, soman, and VX^{13,14}.

Astro chemistry and Geo chemical Research

The Huygens probe of the Cassini-Huygens mission landed one GC-MS on Saturn's largest moon, Titan. The material in the comet 67P/Churyumov-Gerasimenko will be analyzed by the Rosetta mission with a chiral GC-MS in 2014. Significantly enhanced molecular ions, major isomer and structurally significant mass spectral peaks, extended range of low volatility hydrocarbons that are amenable for analysis and unique isotope ratio information make GC-MS valuable for organic geochemical applications⁵².

Medicine and Pharmaceutical Applications

Dozens of congenital metabolic diseases called as inborn error of metabolism are now detectable in newborn by screening tests using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. GC-MS can determine compounds in urine even in minor concentration. These compounds are normally not present but appear in individuals suffering from metabolic disorders. This is easy, effective and efficient way to diagnose the problem like in case of genetic metabolic disorders by a urine test at birth⁵². In combination with isotopic labeling of metabolite, the GCMS is used for determining metabolic activity. Most applications are based on the use of ¹³C labeling and the measurement of ¹³C-¹²C ratios with an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS); an MS with a detector designed to measure a few select ions and return values as ratios. It is useful to detect oils in creams, ointments, lotion etc¹⁶.

Biological and pesticides detections

GC-MS is exclusively used in bio-analysis of blood, urine for the presence of barbiturates, narcotics, alcohols, residual solvents, drugs like anesthetics, anticonvulsant, antihistamine, anti-epileptic drug, sedative hypnotics, narcotics and food items. This technique could be used for detecting adulterations, fatty acid profiling in microbes, presence of free steroids, blood pollutants, metabolites in serum, organo-chlorinated pesticides in river water, drinking water, soft drinks by head space, pesticides in sunflower oil etc.⁵³.

Petrochemical and hydrocarbons analysis

Significantly enhanced molecular ions that are always observed, isomer and structurally significant mass spectral peaks and extended range of low volatility hydrocarbons that are amenable for analysis including waxes up to C₇₄H₁₅₀ makes the GC-MS a most valuable technique. Broad range of petrochemicals, fuels and hydrocarbon mixtures, including gasoline, kerosene, naphthenic acids, diesel fuel, various oil types, transformer oil, biodiesel, wax and broad range of geochemical samples can be analyzed by GC-MS^{38,39}.

Clinical toxicology

Enhanced molecular ions, extended range of compounds amenable for analysis, superior sensitivity for compounds and faster analysis are the main attractive features of the clinical toxicology. The toxin and venoms are identified by GC-MS. It is extensively used in clinical toxicology¹⁷.

Industrial applications

GC-MS is used in industries for the analysis of aromatic solvents, inorganic gases, amino alcohol in water, impurities in styrene, glycol, diols, xylene, allergens in cosmetics etc. GC-MS is used for the characterization of formic acid in acetic acid for industrial use. In Industries acetic acid is important intermediate in coal chemical synthesis. It is used in the production of poly ethylene, cellulose acetate and poly vinyl as well as synthetic fiber and fabrics.

Energy and fuel applications

GC-MS is used for the analysis of aromatic solvents, sulphur, impurities in polypropylene, sulphur in menthane, natural gases, 1,3 butadiene, ethylene, gas oil, unleaded gasoline, polyethene, diesel.oil, unleaded

gasoline, polyethylene, diesel, modified biomass, grafted polymers etc.²⁴. GC-MS has triggered a new arena of research and taken to new heights of impactful presentation and characterization of compounds by its wide range of applications^{17,18}.

Academic research

It is widely used in pure and applied sciences like Chemistry, Polymers, Nanotechnology and Biotechnology etc. It yields useful information that can be used in research publication internationally⁵³.

CONCLUSION

GC-MS is widely used in pharmaceutical industries for analytical research and development, quality control, quality assurance, production, pilot plants departments for active pharmaceutical ingredients (API), bulk drugs and formulations. It is used for process and method development, identification of impurities in API. It is an integral part of research associated with medicinal chemistry (synthesis and characterization of compounds), pharmaceutical analysis (stability testing, impurity profiling), pharmacognosy, pharmaceutical process control and pharmaceutical biotechnology.

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REFERENCES

- Kadhim MJ, Sosa AA, Hameed IH. Evaluation of anti-bacterial activity and bioactive chemical analysis of *Ocimum basilicum* using Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) techniques. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(6): 127-146.
- Mohammed GJ, Kadhim MJ, Hussein HM. Characterization of bioactive chemical compounds from *Aspergillus terreus* and evaluation of antibacterial and antifungal activity. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(6): 889-905.
- Pierangeli G, Vital G and Rivera W. Antimicrobial activity and cytotoxicity of *Chromolaena odorata* (L. f) King and Robinson and *Uncaria perrottetii* (A. Rich) Merr Extracts. *J. Medicinal Plants Res*. 2009; 3(7): 511-518.
- Vyas GD: Soil Fertility Deterioration in Crop Land Due to Pesticide. *Journal of Indian Botanical Society*. 1999; 78: 177-178.
- Kaushik JC, Arya Sanjay, Tripathi NN, Arya S: Antifungal properties of some plant extracts against the damping off fungi of forest nurseries. *Indian Journal of Forestry* 2002; 25: 359-361.
- Chaman Lal and Verma LR: Use of certain bio-products for insect-pest control. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*. 2006; 5(1): 79- 82.
- De-Fatima A, Modolo LV, Conegero LS, Pilli RA, Ferreira CV, Kohn LK, de-Carvalho JE: Lactones and their derivatives: biological activities, mechanisms of action and potential leads for drug design. *Curr. Med. Chem*. 2006; 13: 3371-3384.
- Milne A: Inhalational and local anesthetics reduce tactile and thermal responses in *Mimosa pudica* linn. *Masui* 1993; 1190-3.
- Andrew Marston: Role of advances in chromatographic techniques in phytochemistry. *Phytochemistry* 2007; 68: 2785-2797.
- International Organization for Standardization (2002) Quality management systems-Fundamentals and vocabulary. ISO 9000:2000(E).
- ISO/IEC 17025 (2005) General Requirements for Competence of Testing and Calibration Laboratories. Paragraphs 5.5-5.6.
- Bliesner DM (2006) Validating Chromatographic Methods: A Practical Guide. John Wiley and Sons.
- Amirav A, Gordin A, Poliak M, Fialkov AB (2008) Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry with supersonic molecular beams. *J Mass Spectrom*. 43: 141-163.
- Hameed IH, Altameme HJ, Idan SA. Artemisia annua: Biochemical products analysis of methanolic aerial parts extract and anti-microbial capacity. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 2016; 7(2): 1843- 1868.
- Hussein AO, Mohammed GJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Phytochemical screening of methanolic dried galls extract of *Quercus infectoria* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and Fourier transform-infrared (FT-IR). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(3): 49-59.
- Sosa AA, Bagi SH, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Euphorbia lathyris* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(5): 109-126.
- Altameme HJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Phytochemical analysis of *Urtica dioica* leaves by fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(10): 238-252.
- Mohammed GJ, Omran AM, Hussein HM. Antibacterial and Phytochemical Analysis of *Piper nigrum* using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrum and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(6): 977-996.
- Hamza LF, Kamal SA, Hameed IH. Determination of metabolites products by *Penicillium expansum* and evaluating antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(9): 194-220.
- Jasim H, Hussein AO, Hameed IH, Kareem MA. Characterization of alkaloid constitution and evaluation of antimicrobial activity of *Solanum nigrum* using gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(4): 56-72.

21. Hadi MY, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Nigella sativa* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(2): 8-24.
22. Hameed IH, Ibraheem IA, Kadhim HJ. Gas chromatography mass spectrum and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy analysis of methanolic extract of *Rosmarinus officinalis* leaves. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7 (6): 90-106.
23. Shareef HK, Muhammed HJ, Hussein HM, Hameed IH. Antibacterial effect of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) roscoe and bioactive chemical analysis using gas chromatography mass spectrum. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*. 2016; 32(2): 20-40.
24. Al-Jassaci MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. Secondary Metabolites Analysis of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and Evaluation of Antibacterial Activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(5): 304-315.
25. Mohammed GJ, Al-Jassani MJ, Hameed IH. Antibacterial, Antifungal Activity and Chemical analysis of *Punica grantanum* (Pomegranate peel) using GC-MS and FTIR spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(3): 480-494.
26. Al-Marzoqi AH, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Determination of metabolites products by *Cassia angustifolia* and evaluate antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(2): 25-48.
27. Altameme HJ, Hameed IH, Abu-Serag NA. Analysis of bioactive phytochemical compounds of two medicinal plants, *Equisetum arvense* and *Alchemilla vulgaris* seed using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Malays. Appl. Biol*. 2015; 44(4): 47-58.
28. Hameed IH, Hamza LF, Kamal SA. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Aspergillus niger* by using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015;7(8): 132-163.
29. Hameed IH, Hussein HJ, Kareem MA, Hamad NS. Identification of five newly described bioactive chemical compounds in methanolic extract of *Mentha viridis* by using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7 (7): 107-125.
30. Hussein HM, Hameed IH, Ibraheem OA. Antimicrobial Activity and spectral chemical analysis of methanolic leaves extract of *Adiantum Capillus-Veneris* using GC-MS and FT-IR spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(3): 369-385.
31. Hussein HJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Study of chemical composition of *Foeniculum vulgare* using Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer and gas chromatography - mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(3): 60-89.
32. Kadhim MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. *In vitro* antibacterial, antifungal and phytochemical analysis of methanolic fruit extract of *Cassia fistula*. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*. 2016; 32(2): 10-30.
33. Altameme HJ, Hameed IH, Idan SA, Hadi MY. Biochemical analysis of *Origanum vulgare* seeds by fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(9): 221-237.
34. Hussein HM. Determination of phytochemical composition and ten elements content (CD, CA, CR, CO, FE, PB, MG, MN, NI AND ZN) of *Cardaria Draba* by GC-MS, FT-IR and AAS technique. *Int. J Pharm Bio Sci*. 2016; 7(3): (B) 1009-1017.
35. Hussein HM. Analysis of trace heavy metals and volatile chemical compounds of *Lepidium sativum* using atomic absorption spectroscopy, gas chromatography-mass spectrometric and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 2016; 7(4): 2529-2555.
36. Hameed IH. A new polymorphic positions discovered in mitochondrial DNA hypervariable region HVIII from central and north-central of Iraq. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2016; 27(5): 3250-4.
37. Jaddoa HH, Hameed IH, Mohammed GJ. Analysis of volatile metabolites released by *Staphylococcus aureus* using gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry and determination of its antifungal activity. *Orient J Chem*. 2016; 32(4).
38. Hameed IH, Salman HD, Mohammed GJ. Evaluation of antifungal and antibacterial activity and analysis of bioactive phytochemical compounds of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (Cinnamon bark) using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Orient J Chem*. 2016; 32(4).
39. Hameed IH, Jebor MA, Ommer AJ, Abdulzahra AI. Haplotype data of mitochondrial DNA coding region encompassing nucleotide positions 11,719-12,184 and evaluate the importance of these positions for forensic genetic purposes in Iraq. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2016; 27(2): 1324-1327.
40. Kadhim MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hussein HM. Analysis of bioactive metabolites from *Candida albicans* using (GC-MS) and evaluation of antibacterial activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(7): 655-670.
41. Mohammad A, Imad H. Autosomal STR: From locus information to next generation sequencing technology. *Research Journal of Biotechnology*. 2013.
42. Hameed, I.H., Abdulzahra, A.I., Jebor, M.A., Kqueen, C.Y., Ommer, A.J. Haplotypes and variable position detection in the mitochondrial DNA coding region encompassing nucleotide positions 10,716-11,184. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2015.
43. Ubaid JM, Hussein HM, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive compounds of *Tribolium castaneum* and evaluation of anti-bacterial activity. *International*

- Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(7): 655-670.
44. Altaee N, Kadhim MJ, Hameed IH. Detection of volatile compounds produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from UTI patients by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research*. 2017; 7(6).
45. Altaee N, Kadhim MJ, Hameed IH. Characterization of metabolites produced by *E. coli* and analysis of its chemical compounds using GC-MS. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research*. 2017; 7(6).
46. Hussein JH, Ubaid JM, Hameed IH. Gas chromatography – mass spectrum analysis of volatile components of methanolic leaves extract of *Cordia myxa*. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research*. 2017; 7(6).
47. Kadhim MJ, Kaizal AF, Hameed IH. Medicinal plants used for treatment of rheumatoid arthritis: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2017; 8(11).
48. Hameed, I.H., Al-Rubaye A.F. and Kadhim, M.J. Antimicrobial Activity of Medicinal Plants and Urinary Tract Infections. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2017; 8(11).
49. Kadhim WA, Kadhim, M.J., Hameed, I.H. Antibacterial Activity of Several Plant Extracts Against *Proteus Species*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2017; 8(11).
50. Kadhim MJ. *In Vitro* antifungal potential of *Acinetobacter baumannii* and determination of its chemical composition by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Der Pharma Chemica*, 2016; 8(19): 657-665.
51. Al-Yaseri A, Kadhim WA, Hameed IH. Detection of volatile compounds emitted by *Proteus mirabilis* isolated from UTI patients and its anti-fungal potential. *Der Pharma Chemica*, 2016; 8(19): 671-678.
52. Ubaid JM, Kadhim MJ, Hameed IH. Study of bioactive methanolic extract of *Camponotus fellah* using Gas chromatography – mass spectrum. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research*. 2017; 7(6).
53. Alon T, Amirav A (2006) Isotope abundance analysis methods and software for improved sample identification with supersonic gas chromatography/mass spectrometry. *Rapid Commun Mass Spectrom* 20: 2579-2588.
54. Robert P, Dr. Adams (2007) Identification of Essential Oil Components By Gas Chromatography/Mass spectrometry. 4th edition, Allured Pub Corp.
55. Stein SE, Scott DR (1994) Optimization and testing of mass spectral library search algorithms for compound identification. *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom* 5: 859-866.
56. Handley AJ, Adlard ER (2001) Gas chromatographic techniques and Applications. Sheffield Academic, London.